

The Relationship of Organizational Structure, Performance, and the Type of Technology

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Abstract

In the book, *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965), Joan Woodward presents a comparative empirical study of manufacturing organizations in England. Primarily, Woodward found that the relationship of organizational structure and performance surfaced only by the introduction of an extra variable: the type of technology. The aim of this article is to present the influence of technology on organizational structure and performance in today's hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workplace; through the lens of Woodward's *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965).

“One of the most influential contributors to the Contingency School, Joan Woodward, focused on the relationship between organizational structure and organizational performance” (Vector Study Group, n.d.; Zeller, 2018). In the results of Woodward's comparative empirical study (1950-1959) of 100 manufacturing organizations in England, she noted that the “relationship between structure and performance surfaced only by introducing an extra variable: the type of technology” (Vector Study Group, n.d.; Zeller, 2018). She proposed that the class of ‘core technologies’ that characterize its work also determined an organization's methods. Woodward's approach was unique in that she included process in the dichotomy of nonroutine and routine for identifying changes to processes; and the effects, if any, on controlling and productivity (Barbini & Masino, Eds., 2017, p. 15; Zeller, 2020).

Woodward “argued that differences in the organization of work and in behavior at work could usually be traced to the immediate work situation itself” (Oxford Reference, n.d.; Zeller, 2018). From her viewpoint, the work situation included “the number of levels of management, areas of responsibilities of supervisors, division of functions among specialists, clarity with which roles and duties are defined, amount of written communication, and such like” (Oxford Reference, n.d.; Zeller, 2018). “In her later studies, Woodward (1970) emphasized how changes in markets led to product innovation which then led to changes in technology and subsequently organizational structures”; thereby, changing the work situation and roles (Hinings & Greenwood, 2017, p. 135; Zeller, 2018). Furthermore, Woodward (1965), identified that “in some firms, role relationships prescribed by the organizational structure seemed to be of secondary importance to personal relationships between individuals” (p. 24). On a related note, Woodward (1958, 1980),

recognized that with advances in technology, “the entire concept of authority in industry may have to change” (p. 30; Zeller, 2018).

In her book, *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965), Joan Woodward presents a number of organizational issues; e.g. formal and informal structure; management; technology; production; product development; and, as it was called then, personnel management. In particular, technology is seen as the linchpin for changes in work behavior and in social structure. The specific aim of this article is to present the influence of technology in today’s hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace; through the lens of Joan Woodward’s *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965).

Discussion Points

In 1965, Joan Woodward’s *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965) emphasized the impact of technology on changes in organizational behavior and social structure. Currently, the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workplace is introducing changes in areas highlighted in Woodward’s 1965 research; including the impact of technology (See Zeller, 2018). The question is: Does Woodward’s research in *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965) apply to today’s hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workplace?

The study in the book *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965) offers a wealth of information. The following paragraphs highlight a selection of parts of the study and the relationship, if any, to today’s hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace.

Organizational Structure and Design

Joan Woodward’s *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965)

Identifying the “link between technology, organization, and success, can contribute to the development of techniques to appraise organizational structure; as well as, making it possible to plan organizational change simultaneously with technical change. Primarily, management will not need to see the effects of technical change before modifying organizational structure” (Woodward, 1965, p. 72).

Discussion:

According to conclusions drawn from a November, 2003 internal study conducted by Intel, “wireless mobility changes the way employees work” (McLennan, 2008, p. 175; Zeller, 2017). These technological changes also influence the daily functions of the organizational structure; yet there is minimal systematic knowledge of whether or how this technology has altered structural patterns or conditions that may lead to changes thereof (Tolbert & Hall, 2009; Zeller, 2017).

For example, with the implementation of technology, economies of scale may be realized in the processing of contracts by the sales department (Jost, 2011; Zeller, 2017). However, when technology also includes a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce, the workflow may change; thereby, requiring restructuring. That is, there are challenges from the internal environment as job, work, and business processes, particularly standardized processes, integrate technology.

Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) identified that the dynamics between the organization's processes; e.g. technology in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace; and structure can determine whether a company is in a position to achieve its goals—or not (p. 5411; Zeller, 2017). In their methodology, the researchers' transfer-of-work metrics identifies the end-to-end processes of work from one unit to another (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5412; Zeller, 2017). The framework of the methodology has four phases: (1) to collect source data; (2) to derive a process network; (3) to diagnose 5 problems; and (4) to suggest alternatives of redesigning organizational structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5413; Zeller, 2017).

Since their analysis goes beyond the implications of social relations, the importance of the organizational structure in the business process analysis is recognized (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5423; Zeller, 2017). Furthermore, with this approach, they provide a method to diagnose the critical factors of existing problems before organizational improvements or changes, such as a hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy, are implemented (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5423; Zeller, 2017).

Working Behavior

Joan Woodward's *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965)

In 1959, Dubin maintained “that technology is the single most important single determinant of working behavior. He defined the use of the word technology into two major phases: (1) the tools, instruments, machines, and technical formula basic to the performance of work; and (2) the body of ideas which express the goals of the work, its functional performance, and the rationale of the methods employed” (Woodward, 1965, p. 36).

Discussion:

An historical viewpoint: In Adam Smith's *The Wealth of Nations* centralization, the division of labor in the manufacture of pins to create “a proportionable increase of the productive powers of labour”, was heralded as an ideal approach to achieving strategic initiatives through the workforce (Smith, 1776, p. 12; Zeller, 2016). Then, Frederick Taylor's *The Principles of Scientific Management* time and motion studies promoted standardization as a way to enhance efficiency; i.e., the optimal way to do the job (Taylor, 1917). This division of labor and standardized production processes created an economy of scale, managed by centralized organizational structures that continued to grow well into the 20th century. However, as a result of the beginnings of “mass production in the early part of the 20th century”, “the nature of job and task design evolved” to “routine, machine-paced jobs that afforded little personal control or autonomy” (Vance, 2006; Zeller, 2016). Accordingly, workers “felt dissatisfied with their work, were often absent, and left their employers in search of more meaningful employment” (Vance, 2006; Zeller, 2016).

After World War II, organizational structures were increasingly decentralized; production control and decisions were given to smaller, autonomous units. The benefit to corporate strategies was in the ability of these units to adapt readily to customer requirements and market changes in an increasingly global environment (Reader, 2011). Then, during the 1950s, in an effort to gain employee commitment and to enhance their performance, employers turned toward “the beneficial effects of job enlargement (broadening the scope of job tasks) and job enrichment (providing more complex and challenging tasks)” (Vance, 2006; Zeller, 2016). In the 1970s, the identification of job characteristics; i.e. “skill variety,

task identity, task significance, autonomy, and performance feedback”, were widely accepted by management as the foundation for promoting employee engagement (Vance, 2006; Zeller, 2016). Flatter organizations with less management oversight offered employees broadened job responsibilities (Vance, 2006; Zeller, 2016).

Nowadays, the global economy is dominated by businesses with varied organizational structures (U.S. Department of State, *The History of Small Business*, n.d.; Zeller, 2016). The crux of the situation is that organizations need to “recognize and address the various human and business realities of the company—as a prerequisite for long term success” (eNotes *Organizational Structure*, n.d.; Zeller, 2016). Moreover, the influence of technology on the performance of work in the globalization of the corporate sector requires progressive due diligence as “more work is conducted virtually” (IBM & Seriosity, 2007, p. 3; Zeller, 2018).

Formal / Informal Organization

Joan Woodward’s *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965)

Whereas formal organization is “the stable and explicit pattern of prescribed relationships designed to enable those employed to work together in the achievement of objectives; informal organization is “the pattern of relationship which actually emerges from day-to-day operations” (Woodward, 1965, p. 74).

Discussion:

In the 1930s, psychiatrist, Jacob L. Moreno and psychologist, Helen Jennings, introduced what is considered to be modern social network analysis (SNA) (Freeman, 2011; Zeller, Spring 2018). Basically, “social network analysis (SNA) refers to the collection of methods, techniques, and tools” that is used in the analysis of social networks (von der Aalst & Song, 2004, p. 2; Zeller, Spring 2018). Moreno and Jennings “named their analytical approach, sociometry, to refer to methods used to present the data on interpersonal relationships in graph or matrix form” (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5412; Zeller, Spring 2018). Structural dimensions of social networks are further complicated by the advances in technology that have introduced new settings for when and where work is done. The concept of physical placement continues to evolve as the hybrid (combined virtual / traditional) office environment includes the use of telework centers, collaborative online projects, and rotating schedules (Wineman, Hwang, Kabo, Owen-Smith, & Davis, 2014, Abstract; Zeller, Spring 2018).

Frequently, as is being seen in the hybrid environments, the actual system of roles underlying the organizational processes deviate from the scheduled organizational process that are the foundation for the formal organizational structure (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013; Zeller, Spring 2018). In addition, the informal “social dimension”, whereby people do more than defined by organizational charts, or by job, work, and business process descriptions, is being affected (Bradley & McDonald, 2011; Zeller, Spring 2018). Where and how people “connect” socially, creating a subset of practices for the way that work is actually done, is also changing (Bradley & McDonald, 2011; Zeller, Spring 2018). In some cases, this less formal social network contributes to innovation and improves productivity. In other cases, the social network maintains ingrained, sometimes antiquated, business processes and practices; thus, blocking progressive change.

Role Relationships

Joan Woodward's *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965)

Woodward found that “many firms were less rigid in practice than it appeared on paper. In some firms, role relationships prescribed by the chart seemed to be of secondary importance to personal relationships between individuals” (Woodward, 1956, p. 24).

Discussion:

The main objective of Edward Harvey's research was to “relate organizational technology to organizational structure and to suggest some implications of this linkage for organizational decision-making”; i.e. the internal structure (Harvey, 1967, p. 249; Zeller, Spring 2018). Although organizational charts were used to obtain information for the number of employees and the number of individuals in managerial and supervisory roles for Harvey's research, the charts were not assumed to be “reliable or valid indicators of actual arrangements” (Harvey, 1967, p. 253; Zeller, Spring 2018). Pertinent to Woodward's research is the idea that in Harvey's research, the “the charts were discussed with members of management in an attempt to identify significant discrepancies between formal and informal arrangements” (Harvey, 1967, p. 253; Zeller, Spring 2018).

The issue is that the number of organizations offering the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work options are increasing; thereby, indicating the need to understand the changing personal relationships between individuals and the influence on work. For instance, social capital is described as “the concrete and abstract benefits that can be gained through mutual network relations based on familiarity or friendship” (Sozen, 2012, p. 24; Zeller, Spring 2018). Basically, social capital's structural dimension “refers to the overall pattern of connections between actors--that is, who you reach and how you reach them” (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998, p. 244; Zeller, Spring 2018). Whereas the role relationships prescribed by the charts are significant to understanding formal structure; the personal relationships may be more of an indication of where the work is done.

Communication

Joan Woodward's *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965)

“A frequently encountered organizational problem was that of maintaining an adequate channel of communication between departments which were functionally independent” (Woodward, 1965, p. 137).

Discussion:

Systems Theory views communication “as a system binder, crucial for the survival and growth of the organization. Binding the subsystems together facilitates internal stability and control. By binding the total system to the external environment, communication promotes organizational growth and goal attainment” (Almaney, 1974, Abstract; Zeller, Summer 2018). However, maintaining adequate channels of communication is complicated as the homophonic organization, where the code formed by management is a given; has been replaced by the polyphonic organization that

encourages listening for conversations from multiple venues in order to gain a broader understanding of the issues (Zeller, Summer 2018).

The communication challenges are not limited to United States-based transnational organizations with multiple intra- and inter-departments and a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce. For example, in Japan, “teleworking is a key part of the government’s work-style reform”; hence, organizations are adjusting and adapting to these changes in their environment by facilitating “communication between those clocking in from home and those at the office” (Kyodo, 2018; Zeller Summer 2018).

Strategic Human Resource Management

Joan Woodward’s *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965)

Although the information that the firm was going to spend several million pounds on development was communicated, “it did not help him to understand the significance of his own particular job, or change the frame of reference in which he did it” (Woodward, 1965, p. 174).

Discussion:

The challenge for strategic human resource management is to create the link between the business units and human resources with the talent and resources, whether from virtual offsite or traditional ‘brick and mortar’ offices, to accommodate the organizational strategies and goals (Zeller, Summer 2019). In order to understand the link between the workforce and strategic success, the next step is to research the workforce understanding of the relationship of what they contribute to corporate strategy. For example, if the strategic initiative is to improve call center service then feedback might be solicited to identify what needs to be changed as well as why. In the course of providing feedback and receiving a response, the stakeholders begin to gain an understanding of how what they do on a daily basis influences the firm’s strategic success (Zeller, 2016).

However, in one company, where a major strategy was to improve the response rate to agents, the customer service representatives’ complaints about their software application were largely ignored. Hence, they did not have the information needed to improve the service. The frustration levels grew; the working relationship for both agents and customer service representatives reached hostile levels. In this case, the qualitative data; e.g. feedback, linking strategy to workforce requirements, were not considered (Zeller, 2016).

Recommendations for Future Research

Future studies might expand on the impact of technology on work behavior and social structure through the research of Lisl Klein. Early in her career, she “realized that improved efficiency meant both the cooperation of the workforce and the introduction of new production processes -- and not one without the other” (The Guardian, 2016). Her books, “‘The Meaning of Work’ (1963) and ‘Working Across the Gap’ (2005), take the socio-technical approach, which stresses the importance of studying the interaction between people and technology in the workplace” (The Guardian, 2016).

Furthermore, technology has had a significant impact on the broad fields of Human Resource Management (HRM) and on Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM). Human Resource Management (HRM) theories “help explain how management behaviors and structures can positively or negatively influence employee behavior” (Rowe, 2019; Zeller, 2019). Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) theory “is based, to a large extent, on the assumption that certain organizational goals require certain employee behaviors and that certain human resource strategies produce certain employee behaviors” (Cappelli & Singh, 1992; Schuler & Jackson, 1987; Zeller, 2019). Hence, future research on Human Resource Management (HRM) and Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) with regards to organizational behavior and social structure may help to bridge the role of the workforce to organizational strategy and objectives.

Conclusion ([See Appendix A: The Relationship between Structure, Performance, and Technology](#))

Does Woodward’s research in *Industrial Organization: Theory and Practice* (1965) apply to today’s hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workplace? Woodward proposed that the relationship between organizational structure and performance surfaced only by introducing an extra variable: the type of technology. Her approach was unique in that she included nonroutine and routine processes and the effect, if any, on controlling and productivity. Furthermore, Woodward determined that role relationships, prescribed by the chart; i.e. organizational structure, seemed to be of secondary importance to personal relationships; i.e. social structure, between individuals. Essentially, the actual system of roles underlying the organizational processes deviate from the scheduled organizational process that are the foundation for the formal organizational structure. Hence, as roles and technology changed, social structure and work behavior were also affected.

Based on Woodward’s research highlighted in the discussion section of this article, it appears that the relationship between technology, structure, and performances continues to influence organizations. Fundamentally, that requires creating a proactive and ongoing assessment of changes that have an impact on organizational structure and performance, as influenced by changes in technology in an evolving global market. Moreover, the challenge is identifying those relationships in a transnational organization, with a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce.

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